

1 Simplified expressions for reliability assessments in code calibration

2 Itsaso Arrayago^{a,*}, Hao Zhang^b, Kim J.R. Rasmussen^b

3 ^a *Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, Dept. of Civil and Environmental Engineering, Spain*

4 ^b *The University of Sydney, School of Civil Engineering, Australia*

5 * Corresponding author: Itsaso Arrayago, Jordi Girona 1-3, Building C1, 08034 Barcelona, Spain,

6 itsaso.arrayago@upc.edu

7 **ABSTRACT**

8 First Order Reliability Methods (FORM) have been used by specification committees in the reliability
9 analyses required for the calibration of resistance and safety factors for the past 40 years. However,
10 these methods are iterative, require input information that may not be readily available, and make
11 comparisons between different approaches or design frameworks difficult. This paper presents a set of
12 simplified equations to estimate reliability indices β , resistance factors ϕ and partial safety factors γ_M
13 based on simpler First Order Second Moment (FOSM) considerations for the US and Eurocode
14 frameworks, which are particularized for different load cases, and on the semi-probabilistic approach
15 prescribed in the Eurocode 0. The equations provide direct relationships between the reliability
16 calibration results corresponding to different design frameworks, and can be used to estimate resistance
17 factors as simple cross-checks for the US framework based on the partial safety factors derived for the
18 Eurocode (or vice versa) from basic statistical input information and given target reliability, including
19 when the data available in the literature is insufficient to perform FORM analyses. The accuracy of the
20 proposed equations is assessed against reliability results derived using FORM techniques for an
21 extensive database of steel and stainless steel frames subjected to gravity and combined gravity plus
22 wind load cases collected from the literature, and limitations for their applicability are recommended.
23 The results demonstrate that the set of equations proposed in this paper provides accurate estimations of
24 the reliability index β , resistance factors ϕ and partial safety factors γ_M and can assist specification
25 committees in the process of calibrating suitable ϕ and γ_M -factors.

26 **KEYWORDS**

27 code calibration; structural reliability; reliability index; partial safety factors; resistance factors;
28 FORM; FOSM

29 HIGHLIGHTS

- 30 • Simplified reliability expressions are presented for simple cross-checks in code calibration.
- 31 • Expressions to estimate reliability indices β and resistance ϕ or safety factors γ_M are proposed.
- 32 • Interrelationships between ϕ and γ_M are investigated for gravity and gravity and wind load cases.
- 33 • Expressions allowing a direct comparison between the US and Eurocode frameworks are
34 proposed.
- 35 • The accuracy of the expressions is assessed against FORM results.

36 1. INTRODUCTION

37 New structural verification methods based on direct design approaches are currently being developed
38 for international steel standards as a consequence of the increase of computational power in desktop
39 computers and the better access to advanced finite element software. In these direct design
40 approaches, also referred to as the Direct Design Method, the resistance of structures (or members)
41 can be directly estimated from advanced numerical analyses without requiring further resistance
42 checks, provided the models incorporate all relevant characteristics that affect the strength of the
43 structure, including initial imperfections, nonlinear geometric effects, residual stresses and accurate
44 nonlinear material behaviour. During the last years, significant advances have been made in the
45 development of design recommendations [1-7] and benchmark examples [8] for the direct design of
46 steel structures, the development of new finite elements [9,10], the proposal of strain limits to be used
47 with beam-type finite elements [11,12], and the calibration of system resistance and partial safety
48 factors [13-22]. Since advanced finite element models are capable of accurately predicting the
49 strength and capturing the failure mode of complex structures, direct design approaches can be
50 applied to whole systems (e.g., frames) to fully exploit the benefits arising from load redistribution,
51 spread of plasticity and strain hardening [11-22]. A few structural steel standards already incorporate
52 versions of system-based direct design approaches, including AS/NZS 4100 [23], AISC 360 [24],
53 AISC 370 [25] and prEN 1993-1-14 [26], which adopt the simple Load and Resistance Factor Design
54 (LRFD) design format given in Eq. 1 and Eq. 2 for the US/Australian and Eurocode design
55 frameworks, respectively. In these equations, R_n and R_k are the nominal and characteristic system

56 resistances, respectively, Q_{ni} and Q_{ki} denote the nominal and characteristic structural loads, ϕ and γ_M
57 are the system resistance and partial safety factors for resistance that account for the uncertainties in
58 the system strength, and γ_i are the load factors corresponding to the load combination rules specified
59 in the load standards.

$$\phi R_n \geq \sum \gamma_i Q_{n,i} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

$$R_k / \gamma_M \geq \sum \gamma_i Q_{k,i} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

60 The specifications [23-26] require that a level of reliability equivalent to that obtained from member-
61 based design be achieved when using system-based approaches, but they do not provide system
62 resistance ϕ or partial safety factors γ_M for use in system-based direct design. Thus, recent research
63 efforts have focused on the calibration of system factors to guarantee that the target reliability levels
64 required by the different specifications are met, based on robust reliability frameworks built for
65 different types of structures and materials [14-22]. Nevertheless, the calibration of system factors is
66 generally carried out to one of the existing specifications or design frameworks (e.g., the Australian,
67 US or Eurocode frameworks), using the load combinations and the load statistics specific to that
68 framework. Thus, the extension of design recommendations to other frameworks with different load
69 models and particular load combinations is not direct. It requires the use of advanced techniques and
70 that all the basic input information (i.e., statistical characterization of the system strength and loads) is
71 available.

72 With the aim of assisting researchers and specification committees use information in the literature
73 to develop new recommendations for different design frameworks, the derivation of simple
74 expressions that estimate the level of reliability associated with a certain resistance or partial safety
75 factor is useful, including expressions that allow performing simple cross-checks on more accurate
76 reliability analyses. Furthermore, having expressions that directly relate the reliability calibration
77 results for different design frameworks through a few basic variables for a rapid comparison, or that
78 estimate suitable resistance (or safety) factors for a target reliability index based on the partial safety
79 (or resistance) factors proposed in a different framework for a different target reliability, is also useful
80 for researchers and specification committees.

81 This paper presents a set of simple expressions to carry out reliability calculations without
82 requiring the use of more advanced (but iterative) techniques. Although the proposed simplified
83 equations are not intended to replace these advanced reliability analysis procedures for code
84 calibration, they serve different purposes, (i) they provide a simple cross-check on the more accurate
85 reliability calculations, (ii) they allow a direct comparison between codes, notably Eurocodes and US
86 codes, and (iii) they provide a means of calculating partial factors for members and connections
87 whose nominal strength is based on tests, as prescribed in some international specifications such as
88 prEN 1990 [27] and AISI S100 [28]. The derivation of the expressions and their application to
89 different load cases is presented in Section 2, while Section 3 provides an overview of the system
90 reliability studies on steel frames available in the literature, from which a database for the evaluation
91 of the developed expressions has been assembled. Section 4 assesses the accuracy of the derived
92 equations to predict reliability indices and resistance or partial safety factors, while in Section 5
93 expressions for the direct comparison of reliability levels in the US and Eurocode design frameworks
94 are developed and assessed.

95 **2. DERIVATION OF SIMPLIFIED EXPRESSIONS FOR β , ϕ AND γ_M**

96 2.1. GENERAL

97 The safety or failure of a structure has been traditionally quantified through its probability of failure
98 P_f (i.e., the probability of load effects S exceeding the structural resistance R or reaching a certain
99 limit state), which can be determined as $P_f = P(R \leq S)$. Introducing the limit state function $g = R -$
100 S , then $P_f = P(g \leq 0)$, since $g \leq 0$ defines the failure domain. Often, the reliability index β is used
101 as an indirect measurement of P_f , which is calculated from $\beta = \Phi^{-1}(1 - P_f)$, where Φ^{-1} is the
102 inverse standard normal distribution function. One option to compute the probability of failure is to
103 sample the variables of the limit state function randomly and to obtain the probability using direct
104 Monte Carlo simulation (MCS) techniques. However, this method requires a large number of
105 simulations to accurately capture the lower tail of the density probability function and thus alternative
106 methodologies have been developed over the last decades [29], including First Order Second Moment
107 (FOSM) and First Order Reliability Methods (FORM).

108 Broadly speaking, code-based reliability traditionally adopts First Order Second Moment (FOSM)
109 reliability procedures, which linearize the limit state function and use only the first two moments
110 (mean and standard deviation) to represent random variables, ignoring higher moments such as the
111 skew and flatness [30]. Although FOSM procedures are simple and useful, refinements have been
112 developed from the original method to overcome some of its drawbacks. These include the extension
113 of the method to nonlinear limit state functions and modifications that allow approximating the actual
114 probability distributions of the random variables using equivalent normal distributions – since the
115 probabilistic distributions of random variables are often known. These new methods are usually
116 referred to as First Order Reliability Methods (FORM) and adopt iterative solution schemes [29,31]
117 which convert non-normal random variables to equivalent normal distributions. Since FORM
118 techniques were shown to provide reliability indices only marginally lower than those obtained using
119 direct Monte Carlo simulations (with deviations of about 2-5%) [14], they were deemed sufficiently
120 accurate to carry out reliability studies for code calibration, and have been systematically used in the
121 calibration of resistance factors, including the system factors derived in [14-22] for the direct design
122 of steel and stainless steel frames.

123 2.2. ESTIMATION OF β , ϕ AND γ_M USING FOSM METHODS

124 The FOSM gives an exact solution of the reliability index when both the resistance R and the load
125 effect S are normal (or lognormal) random variables. For a steel structural member, the resistance R
126 can often be modelled as a lognormal. If the load effect S is also a lognormal, the limit state function
127 can be written as $g = \ln(R/S)$. Note that $\ln(R/S)$ is a normal random variable. In this case, the
128 reliability index can be computed using the mean and standard deviation of $\ln(R/S)$, as per $\beta =$
129 $\overline{\ln(R/S)} / \sigma_{\ln(R/S)}$. β represents the distance from $\overline{\ln(R/S)}$ to the origin in standard deviation units and
130 the area under $\ln(R/S) \leq 0$ is the probability of failure P_f (see Figure 1); in other cases (non-normal
131 or non-lognormal distributions), β provides a relative measure of the structural safety. Note that
132 throughout this paper \bar{X} , σ_X and V_X represent the mean value, the standard deviation and the
133 coefficient of variation (COV), respectively, of the random variable X . Using small variance
134 approximations, then $\overline{\ln(R/S)} = \ln(\bar{R}/\bar{S})$ and $\sigma_{\ln(R/S)} = \sqrt{V_R^2 + V_S^2}$, and the reliability index β is

135 approximately given by the relationship shown in Eq. 3, which was the basis for the development of
 136 the probability-based LRFD criteria for steel structures in [32].

$$\beta = \frac{\ln(\bar{R}/\bar{S})}{\sqrt{V_R^2 + V_S^2}} \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

137 While the values for \bar{R} and V_R can be obtained from theoretical resistance models or extensive
 138 numerical simulations that account for all relevant uncertainties, \bar{S} and V_S depend on the type of
 139 loading investigated, the load combination and the statistical models (mean and coefficient of
 140 variation) assumed for the different loads in the design framework considered. Thus, to develop
 141 simplified expressions for reliability calibrations it is necessary to estimate \bar{R}/\bar{S} and $\sqrt{V_R^2 + V_S^2}$ as
 142 functions of the basic statistical parameters used in reliability analyses, including stochastic models
 143 for loads, suitable load combinations (load factors), stochastic models for resistance, etc. From the
 144 general LRFD design equation for the US framework given in Eq. 1, assuming that the structure (or
 145 member) is at its limit state and defining a new coefficient C as $C_{US} = \sum \gamma_i Q_{n,i}/\bar{S}$, \bar{R}/\bar{S} can be written
 146 as $\bar{R}/\bar{S} = C_{US}/\phi \cdot \bar{R}/R_n$, from which a direct relationship can be established between β and ϕ as a
 147 function of the coefficient C_{US} , the mean-to-nominal resistance ratio \bar{R}/R_n and the coefficients of
 148 variation for the resistance V_R and load effects $V_{S,US}$, as shown in Eq. 4. If this equation is inverted,
 149 the expression that provides the required resistance factor ϕ for a certain level of reliability β can be
 150 obtained, as given by Eq. 5.

$$\beta = \frac{\ln\left(C_{US} \frac{\bar{R}}{R_n} \frac{1}{\phi}\right)}{\sqrt{V_R^2 + V_{S,US}^2}} \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

$$\phi = C_{US} \frac{\bar{R}}{R_n} \exp\left[-\beta \sqrt{V_R^2 + V_{S,US}^2}\right] \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

151 For the calculation of C_{US} and $V_{S,US}$, the load combinations prescribed in the ASCE 7 [33]
 152 Specification and load statistics specific to the US framework should be considered. Eq. 5 is very
 153 similar to the expression prescribed in Chapter K of the AISI S100 [28] Specification, as developed in
 154 [32,34] for the calibration of ϕ -factors when the resistance of members is determined through testing,
 155 where the mean-to-nominal resistance ratio \bar{R}/R_n is calculated as the product of the mean values of

156 the material factor M_m , the fabrication factor F_m and the professional factor P_m , while V_R depends on
 157 the coefficients of variation of the same factors. Despite being originally prescribed for studies based
 158 on experimental results, this approach has been systematically used by researchers to carry out
 159 reliability calibrations when proposing design expressions for cross-section and member resistance
 160 based on hybrid databases comprising experimental and numerical results. In the AISI S100 equation,
 161 the C_{US} and $V_{S,US}$ parameters representing uncertainties in the loads are expressed as C_ϕ and V_Q , and
 162 are calculated for the gravity load combination with a dead-to-live load ratio of 1/5, the load ratio
 163 commonly used for cold-formed steel structures [28,30].

164 Equivalent relationships to Eq. 4 and Eq. 5 can be derived for the Eurocode framework following
 165 the same procedure and considering the Eurocode LRFD equation Eq. 2, as given in Eq. 6 and Eq.
 166 7, in which C_{EN} and $V_{S,EN}$ are to be determined using suitable characteristic load values and load
 167 factors according to the different parts of Eurocode 1 [35,36] and the load combinations prescribed in
 168 prEN 1990 [27].

$$\beta = \frac{\ln\left(C_{EN} \frac{\bar{R}}{R_k} \gamma_M\right)}{\sqrt{V_R^2 + V_{S,EN}^2}} \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

$$\gamma_M = \frac{1}{C_{EN} \bar{R}/R_k} \exp\left[\beta \sqrt{V_R^2 + V_{S,EN}^2}\right] \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

169 Eq. 4 and Eq. 6 can be used to predict reliability indices β without performing FORM analyses,
 170 while Eq. 5 and Eq. 7 provide a direct estimation of the resistance or partial safety factors required to
 171 meet certain levels of target reliability specific to the design framework under consideration.

172 2.3. APPLICATION TO PARTICULAR LOAD CASES

173 The parameters C_{US} (or C_{EN}) and $V_{S,US}$ (or $V_{S,EN}$) defined in the previous Section depend not only on
 174 the design framework considered in the analysis, but also on the load cases investigated. The
 175 development of these factors for different load cases is further investigated in this Section, including
 176 the gravity load (dead and live loads), wind load and combined gravity plus wind load cases. Since the
 177 calibration coefficients C and coefficients of variation of the load effects V_S depend on the load
 178 combinations and the statistics assumed for the loads, they typically exhibit different values in the US

179 and Eurocode frameworks; however, the expressions presented herein are generic and can be used in
 180 both design frameworks. It should be noted that although the development of the expressions in this
 181 Section is based on the nominal load concept, which would correspond to the US design framework,
 182 equivalent equations can be obtained if based on the characteristic loads typically used in the
 183 Eurocode framework. For simplicity, equations have not been duplicated and only expressions that
 184 use nominal loads are provided.

185 2.3.1. Gravity loads, $G + Q$

186 When the reliability of structures under gravity loads is evaluated, different dead-to-live load ratios
 187 $\zeta = G_n/Q_n$ are customarily considered, where G_n and Q_n are the nominal dead and live load,
 188 respectively, since the calibrated reliability indices depend on the load ratio ζ [14-22]. The general
 189 form of the load combination under gravity loads is $\sum \gamma_i Q_{n,i} = \gamma_G G_n + \gamma_Q Q_n$, where γ_G and γ_Q are
 190 the load factors for the dead and live load, respectively. The mean value of the total load \bar{S} can be re-
 191 written as $\bar{S} = \bar{G} + \bar{Q}$, where \bar{G} and \bar{Q} are the mean values of the dead and live loads, from which the
 192 $C_{GQ,j}$ coefficient under gravity loads shown in Eq. 8 can be obtained. Note that the sub-index j refers
 193 to the US or the Eurocode design frameworks, and that the $C_{GQ,j}$ coefficient depends on the load
 194 factors (γ_i), the dead-to-live load ratio ζ and the load statistics (\bar{G}/G_n and \bar{Q}/Q_n).

$$C_{GQ,j} = \frac{\zeta \gamma_G + \gamma_Q}{\zeta \frac{\bar{G}}{G_n} + \frac{\bar{Q}}{Q_n}} \quad \text{Eq. 8}$$

195 Similarly, the coefficient of variation of the total gravity loads $V_{S,GQ,j}$ can be determined utilising that
 196 $V_S = \sigma_S/\bar{S}$ and $\sigma_S^2 = \sigma_G^2 + \sigma_Q^2$ (assuming G and Q are uncorrelated), as per in Eq. 9, which also
 197 depends on the ζ -ratio and the stochastic models adopted for the loads (\bar{G}/G_n , \bar{Q}/Q_n , V_G and V_Q).
 198 Information about the load models for the different load types and different design frameworks can be
 199 found in the literature [21,22,37-39] and is summarized in Table 1, which reports the mean value,
 200 coefficient of variation and distribution type for the most common loads for the US and Eurocode
 201 frameworks.

$$V_{S,GQ,j} = \frac{\left[\zeta^2 \left(\frac{\bar{G}}{G_n} \right)^2 V_G^2 + \left(\frac{\bar{Q}}{Q_n} \right)^2 V_Q^2 \right]^{1/2}}{\zeta \left(\frac{\bar{G}}{G_n} \right) + \left(\frac{\bar{Q}}{Q_n} \right)} \quad \text{Eq. 9}$$

202 In particular, the values of the calibration coefficient C_ϕ and the coefficient of variation of the load
 203 effects V_Q prescribed in the AISI S100 [28] Specification are 1.52 and 0.21, respectively, which
 204 correspond to the C_{GQ} and $V_{S,GQ}$ parameters given in Eq. 8 and Eq. 9 when $\gamma_G = 1.20$, $\gamma_Q = 1.60$,
 205 $\zeta = 0.2$ and the load statistics reported in Table 1 for the US framework are adopted. The equations
 206 derived herein, together with those presented in the next sub-sections, give a better estimation of the
 207 C_ϕ and V_Q coefficients for load cases different to $\zeta = 0.2$ because they are broader and adopt general
 208 cases of ζ instead of assuming fixed values of the coefficients, and are equivalent to the equations
 209 given in [30]. According to AISI S100 [28], these general equations should be adopted in special
 210 situations when loading cases deviate from the gravity load case assumed.

211 2.3.2. Wind loads, W

212 If only wind loads are considered in the analysis, the derivation of the $C_{W,j}$ and $V_{S,W,j}$ coefficients is
 213 simple since the limit state function and the design equation only depend on one load type. These
 214 coefficients are as shown in Eq. 10 and Eq. 11, in which γ_W , \bar{W}/W_n and V_W are the load factor, the
 215 mean-to-nominal ratio and the coefficient of variation of the wind load, as defined in load standards
 216 [27,33] and reported in Table 1.

$$C_{W,j} = \frac{\gamma_W}{\bar{W}/W_n} \quad \text{Eq. 10}$$

$$V_{S,W,j} = V_W \quad \text{Eq. 11}$$

217 2.3.3. Combined gravity plus wind loads, $G + Q_{apt} + W$

218 When load combinations including imposed live loads and wind loads are investigated, it is necessary
 219 to consider the arbitrary-point-in-time live load Q_{apt} instead of the 50-year maximum live load Q . As
 220 for gravity loads in Section 2.3.1, to derive the $C_{GQ_{apt}W,j}$ and $V_{S,GQ_{apt}W,j}$ coefficients for combined
 221 gravity plus wind loads, different ratios of dead-to-live loads $\zeta = G_n/Q_n$ and wind-to-live loads $\delta =$
 222 W_n/Q_n need to be considered. Following similar steps to those adopted for the gravity load case, the

223 expressions shown in Eq. 12 and Eq. 13 can be derived to estimate the $C_{GQ_{apt}W,j}$ and $V_{S,GQ_{apt}W,j}$
 224 coefficients, where \bar{Q}_{apt} is the mean value of the of the arbitrary-point-in-time live load.

$$C_{GQ_{apt}W,j} = \frac{\zeta\gamma_G + \gamma_Q + \delta\gamma_W}{\zeta \frac{\bar{G}}{G_n} + \frac{\bar{Q}_{apt}}{Q_n} + \delta \frac{\bar{W}}{W_n}} \quad \text{Eq. 12}$$

$$V_{S,GQ_{apt}W,j} = \frac{\left[\zeta^2 \left(\frac{\bar{G}}{G_n} \right)^2 V_G^2 + \left(\frac{\bar{Q}_{apt}}{Q_n} \right)^2 V_{Q_{apt}}^2 + \delta^2 \left(\frac{\bar{W}}{W_n} \right)^2 V_W^2 \right]^{1/2}}{\zeta \frac{\bar{G}}{G_n} + \frac{\bar{Q}_{apt}}{Q_n} + \delta \frac{\bar{W}}{W_n}} \quad \text{Eq. 13}$$

225 2.4. EUROCODE SEMI-PROBABILISTIC APPROACH

226 According to Annex C of prEN 1990 [27], the calibration of partial safety factors for resistance can be
 227 carried out based on First Order Reliability Methods or on full probabilistic methods. Since it is often
 228 not possible to use the full probabilistic method due to the lack of statistical data, the approach
 229 generally adopted for the calibration of partial safety factors or the safety assessment of new design
 230 expressions in the Eurocode framework is the semi-probabilistic procedure given in Annex D of
 231 prEN 1990 [27]. For the case of a large number of tests ($n > 100$), the partial safety factor for
 232 resistance γ_M can be determined from Eq. 14,

$$\gamma_M = \frac{R_k}{b\bar{R}\exp[-\alpha_R\beta\theta - 0.5\theta^2]} \quad \text{Eq. 14}$$

233 where b is the mean of the model factor, α_R is the First Order Reliability Method sensitivity factor for
 234 the resistance and θ is a parameter that accounts for the variability in the design model and the basic
 235 random variables, given in Eq. 15. Note that in prEN 1990 [27] the θ parameter is referred to as Q ,
 236 but a different notation is adopted in this paper to avoid confusion with the live load Q . The θ -
 237 parameter depends on the total coefficient of variation of the resistance V_r and can be estimated from
 238 Eq. 16 through the coefficients of variation of the model factor and the basic input parameters, V_δ and
 239 V_{rt} .

$$\theta = \sqrt{\ln(1 + V_r^2)} \quad \text{Eq. 15}$$

$$(1 + V_r^2) = (1 + V_\delta^2) \cdot (1 + V_{rt}^2) \quad \text{Eq. 16}$$

240 One of the main features of the Eurocode semi-probabilistic procedure is that it clearly separates the
 241 load and resistance sides of the probabilistic problem, making the calibration of the partial safety
 242 factors for the resistance independent of the variability of the loads. This is achieved by allocating
 243 constant fractions of the target reliability index to the resistance and the load sides through the factors
 244 α_R and α_E , which correspond to the First Order Reliability Method sensitivity factors. For the cases in
 245 which the standard deviation of the load effects and the resistance do not deviate much ($0.16 <$
 246 $\sigma_E/\sigma_R < 7.6$), the values adopted for the sensitivity factors are $\alpha_R = 0.8$ and $\alpha_E = -0.7$, where
 247 $\sqrt{\alpha_R^2 + \alpha_E^2} \approx 1.0$. The adoption of fixed values for these sensitivity factors results in a non-iterative
 248 procedure, in which the value of the partial safety factor for resistance γ_M can be obtained directly.
 249 The approach also assumes that the resistance and model factor follow lognormal distributions [40].
 250 Eq. 14 can be further simplified if the total coefficient of variation is small ($V_r < 0.20$), since the
 251 $0.5\theta^2$ term in the same equation can be neglected [27], and if model uncertainties are accounted for
 252 implicitly in the resistance function, in which case $b = 1$ and $V_r = V_{rt}$. Using these simplifications,
 253 the equation to estimate the partial safety factor for the resistance γ_M using the Eurocode semi-
 254 probabilistic approach is shown in Eq. 17, from which the expression that provides the level of
 255 reliability β achieved for a given value of partial safety factor γ_M can be derived, as given by Eq. 18.

$$\gamma_M = \frac{1}{\bar{R}/R_k} \exp[\alpha_R \beta \theta] \quad \text{Eq. 17}$$

$$\beta = \frac{1}{\alpha_R \theta} \ln \left(\frac{\bar{R}}{R_k} \gamma_M \right) \quad \text{Eq. 18}$$

256 These equations are equivalent to Eq. 6 and Eq. 7 derived in Section 2.2, but are based on the
 257 Eurocode semi-probabilistic approach instead of using FOSM methods. The main difference between
 258 the Eurocode and other specifications based on FOSM procedures (such as AISI S100-16 [28] or
 259 AS/NZS 4600 [41]) is that, unlike the expression given in Eq. 7, the partial safety factor γ_M estimated
 260 using Eq. 17 does not depend on the load combination considered (γ_G , γ_Q and γ_W factors) or the
 261 variability of the loads (mean values and COVs of the load distributions).

262 The comparison of the γ_M partial safety factors calculated using the Eurocode semi-probabilistic
 263 approach (Eq. 17) and FOSM procedures (Eq. 7), in terms of $\gamma_{M,EN}/\gamma_{M,FOSM}$ ratios, is presented in

264 Figure 2. Different load cases, including gravity load scenarios with dead-to-live load ratios ζ of 1.0,
265 0.5 and 0.2 and wind load cases are investigated, showing that the $\gamma_{M,EN}/\gamma_{M,FOSM}$ ratios reduce for
266 increasing values of the reliability index β for all load cases. In this comparison, a coefficient of
267 variation equal to $V_r = V_R = 0.10$ was assumed for the variability of the resistance, which is a typical
268 value for steel structures [13]. The results in Figure 2 also show that for gravity load cases $\gamma_{M,EN}$
269 factors are higher than their $\gamma_{M,FOSM}$ counterparts, although the difference is reduced as the dead-to-
270 live load ratio ζ decreases, and equivalent results are obtained for $\zeta = 0.2$ at the 3.8-4.0 reliability
271 index range, while the deviations between the two methods are more pronounced for wind loads, with
272 the $\gamma_{M,EN}$ -factors being lower than $\gamma_{M,FOSM}$ in the intermediate-to-high β -range.

273 3. SYSTEM RELIABILITY CALIBRATION FOR STEEL FRAMES

274 To contribute to the widespread and normalization of system-based direct design approaches, recent
275 research efforts have focussed on the statistical characterization of the resistance of steel structural
276 systems and, through comprehensive reliability calibrations, on the recommendation of system
277 resistance and partial safety factors that meet the level of reliability required by the different
278 international specifications [14-22]. Based on the limit state functions $g = R - G - Q$ and $g = R -$
279 W for the gravity and wind load cases, respectively, these studies have adopted First Order Reliability
280 Method techniques to compute the reliability indices β associated to different values of resistance ϕ
281 and partial safety γ_M factors for steel structures. This process relies on an accurate characterization of
282 the system strength statistics, the implementation of efficient FORM algorithms and the adoption of
283 suitable target reliability indices for the design frameworks under investigation. This Section provides
284 a summary of the different features in system reliability calibration.

285 3.1. STATISTICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF SYSTEM STRENGTH

286 To provide comprehensive design recommendations for the direct design of steel systems, it is
287 fundamental to choose representative structural types that cover the full range of system behaviour,
288 including different types of failure, regular/irregular system configurations, different connection
289 types, etc. The statistics of the strength of these systems under different loading conditions can be
290 determined from comprehensive experimental programmes or extensive advanced finite element (FE)

291 simulations. Although both tests and numerical data can be considered when determining the strength
292 of members, the use of experimental programmes to characterize system strength distributions is
293 unfeasible and advanced FE simulations need to be used.

294 While the presence of random properties is inherent in the specimens used for testing, it is
295 necessary to sample randomly the variables that affect the strength of the systems (i.e., material and
296 geometric properties, initial geometric imperfections, residual stresses, and the behaviour of
297 connections) when numerical simulations are used. The basic requirements for this are to build
298 advanced finite element models capable of accounting for all geometric and material nonlinearities
299 and to have knowledge about the variability of each of the random variables involved. In general, the
300 determination of the probabilistic models for system strength entails a large number of simulations,
301 although it can be reduced to typically 250-350 simulations through the adoption of Latin Hypercube
302 Sampling (LHS) techniques [14-22]. Besides, it is necessary to include an additional random variable
303 that accounts for the uncertainties associated with the assumptions and approximations made when
304 building the FE models, i.e., the model factor. Based on the methodology described above, the
305 distribution type, mean value and coefficient of variation of the system strength can be determined,
306 which in combination with the nominal system strength determined following the requirements
307 prescribed in the relevant specifications, constitute the fundamental input information in carrying out
308 reliability calibrations (i.e., \bar{R}/R_n and V_R).

309 3.2. RELIABILITY CALIBRATIONS USING FORM

310 Using the system strength statistics determined from experimental results or numerical simulations
311 and the stochastic models for the loads relevant to the design framework and loading types under
312 consideration available in the literature (and summarized in Table 1), different sets of reliability
313 indices β can be computed for a range of resistance ϕ and partial safety γ_M factors using scripts
314 coding the FORM methodology (e.g., see [14-22]) and considering the load factors prescribed in the
315 ASCE 7 [33] and prEN 1990 [27] standards for the US and Eurocode design frameworks,
316 respectively. These sets of $\beta - \phi$ and $\beta - \gamma_M$ relationships established using the FORM method have
317 been utilised in previous studies [14-22] to derive suitable system factors that meet the reliability
318 levels required by international specifications (i.e., prescribed target reliability indices) and to develop

319 design recommendations for the direct design of steel systems. The results have also been used in the
320 subsequent Sections of this paper as benchmark values for reliability indices β and resistance ϕ or
321 partial safety γ_M factors in the assessment of the derived simplified equations.

322 3.3. TARGET RELIABILITIES IN THE US AND EUROCODE FRAMEWORKS

323 Target reliability indices β_0 are prescribed in the international standards for a variety of structure
324 classes and limit states, including ultimate limit states and serviceability limit states. These indices
325 generally correspond to 50-year reference periods (service life for common steel buildings), and thus
326 reliability calibrations are usually performed using input information that corresponds to this period,
327 including the statistical characterization of the maximum expected loads acting on the structure.
328 prEN 1990 [27] prescribes a minimum value of the target reliability index of $\beta_0 = 3.8$ for ultimate
329 limit states in Consequence Class 2 (CC2) structures and a reference period of 50 years, although for
330 structures dominated by wind loads a lower reliability of $\beta_0 = 2.8$ is usually accepted [22,42].
331 Likewise, the target reliability indices adopted in the ASCE 7 [33] Specification for Risk Category I
332 and II structures are $\beta_0 = 2.5$ and $\beta_0 = 3.0$, respectively, although for wind load cases the reliability
333 index has been found to be consistently lower than for gravity load cases [15,17,43-45]. However, if
334 the recently updated wind load model proposed in [37] and reported in Table 1 is used when
335 performing reliability calibrations in the US framework, higher reliability indices, equivalent to those
336 obtained for gravity loads, are obtained because these new statistics consider part of the hidden
337 reliability present in the wind load model related to the bias in the wind directionality factor [37]. For
338 code calibration, an intermediate value between $\beta_0 = 2.5$ and $\beta_0 = 3.0$ (e.g., $\beta_0 = 2.8$) can be
339 adopted.

340 3.4. PREVIOUS STUDIES ON SYSTEM FACTOR CALIBRATION

341 To date, reliability studies on structural systems have been conducted on hot-rolled steel [14-17],
342 cold-formed steel [18-20] and cold-formed stainless steel [21-22] structures under different loading
343 conditions with the aim of calibrating system resistance or partial safety factors, featuring planar
344 frames, spatial frames and portal frames. These studies adopted the methodology described in the
345 previous Sections, and conducted extensive numerical simulations to characterize the stochastic

346 models for the system strength of a variety of structures. The system resistance factors calibrated for
347 steel structures and the target reliability indices discussed in the previous Section were around $\phi_s =$
348 $0.80 - 0.85$ for gravity loads [14-16,18,19] and combined gravity plus wind load cases
349 [14,15,17,18,20] in the US design framework. Due to higher overstrength ratios (i.e., mean-to-
350 nominal yield stress ratios), higher system resistance factors of around $\phi_s = 0.90 - 0.95$ were
351 proposed for stainless steel portal frames in [21-22], while for the Eurocode framework system partial
352 safety factors of $\gamma_{M,s} = 1.15 - 1.20$ were found to be appropriate.

353 The \bar{R}/R_n and V_R results derived in these previous studies, which are available in the literature,
354 have been collected herein and used to assess the accuracy of the simplified expressions presented in
355 Section 2. Table 2 presents the database collected from [14-22], summarizing the frame type and load
356 case analysed in each subset of data, in addition to the total number of frames investigated and the
357 ranges of mean-to-nominal resistance ratios \bar{R}/R_n and coefficients of variation for the resistance
358 distributions V_R . Within each subset of data, results corresponding to different types of frames (frames
359 with and without rigid diaphragm, hinged or rigid beam-to-column connections, compact and slender
360 sections) are included. It should be noticed that since the research works from which the \bar{R}/R_n and V_R
361 values were obtained focused on the development of system-based direct design recommendations for
362 steel and stainless steel structures [14-22], the resistance and partial safety factors considered in this
363 study correspond to system factors. However, the derived simplified equations apply to both member-
364 based and system-based reliability calibrations, as do the conclusions drawn in Section 6. Similarly,
365 the same equations and conclusions would also be valid if strength distributions were determined
366 using experimental data instead of advanced FE simulations.

367 **4. ESTIMATION OF RELIABILITY INDICES β OR RESISTANCE ϕ AND PARTIAL** 368 **SAFETY γ_M FACTORS**

369 This Section evaluates the accuracy of the different simplified equations derived in Section 2 for the
370 estimation of reliability indices β and resistance ϕ or partial safety γ_M factors against the
371 corresponding values calculated using the FORM reliability procedures described in Section 3. While

372 for the US framework the equations derived using the FOSM method are considered, for the Eurocode
373 framework expressions based on both the FOSM and semi-probabilistic approaches are analysed.

374 4.1. ASSESSMENT OF THE ESTIMATED RELIABILITY INDICES β

375 The reliability indices calibrated using the FORM method for the steel and stainless steel frames
376 collected in the database are compared with the β -values predicted from Eq. 4 and Eq. 6 for the US
377 and Eurocode design frameworks, respectively, and with the values calculated using the Eurocode
378 semi-probabilistic approach (Eq. 18). The resistance and partial safety factors considered were
379 defined based on values of practical interest, ranging approximately between $\phi = 0.80 - 1.00$ and
380 $\gamma_M = 1.00 - 1.30$. Since the database included frames under gravity and combined gravity plus wind
381 load cases, suitable C and V_S coefficients were considered and calculated according to the expressions
382 presented in Section 2.3 for the approaches based on the FOSM method. For the gravity load case,
383 different dead-to-live load ratios ζ were assumed, while the analysis for the combined gravity plus
384 wind load case also included a range of gravity-to-wind load ratios. It should be noticed that the
385 combined load cases investigated in this paper and reported in [14,15,17,20,22] correspond to push-
386 over type analyses, in which the uncertainties of the gravity loads are implicitly accounted for in the
387 stochastic models reported for the resistance (i.e., \bar{R}/R_n and V_R values). Thus, only wind load
388 statistics need to be considered in the calibration of β , γ_M or ϕ , and the expressions presented in
389 Section 2.3.2 for wind loads only have been considered instead of those reported in Section 2.3.3,
390 which would be suitable for load cases in which all loads are simultaneously applied.

391 The assessment of the accuracy of Eq. 4, Eq. 6 and Eq. 18 to estimate reliability indices is
392 presented in Figure 3, in which the β -values determined from FORM analyses (β_{FORM}) are compared
393 with the β -values predicted using the proposed method β_{pred} (i.e., computed using Eq. 4, Eq. 6 and
394 Eq. 18) and plotted against the reference β_{FORM} -values. The results are presented separately for the
395 different load cases and the different simplified procedures investigated in this paper, including the
396 FOSM-based equations for the US and Eurocode frameworks, and the semi-probabilistic approach
397 prescribed in Annex D of prEN 1990 [27] for the Eurocode framework. It should be noticed that
398 although dead-to-live ratios ζ ranging between 0.2 - 1.0 have been analysed for the gravity load case,

399 for simplicity, Figure 3 only shows results corresponding to $\zeta = 0.5$ and $\zeta = 0.2$, which are the
400 common load ratios for steel structures [18,21] and cold-formed steel structures [28,30], respectively.
401 According to the results shown in Figure 3(a) and (b), the estimation of the reliability index for the
402 gravity plus wind load case is slightly more accurate than for the gravity load case for the FOSM-
403 based approaches, and the $\beta_{pred}/\beta_{FORM}$ values for gravity plus wind loads show a considerably lower
404 scatter and more consistent results over the full range of β_{FORM} -values. Conversely, the results for
405 gravity loads are more scattered and the accuracy in the prediction of the reliability index decreases
406 with increasing values of the reliability index.

407 In general, the results for the US and Eurocode frameworks exhibit the same trend for each of the
408 load cases considered when the reliability index is estimated using FOSM-based approaches. Hence,
409 the accuracy observed for the two design frameworks is similar. However, since the absolute values of
410 the reliability indices calibrated for gravity loads in the Eurocode framework are higher than for the
411 US framework, the accuracy of the β_{pred} -values is somehow lower for the Eurocode. Regarding the
412 Eurocode semi-probabilistic approach, Figure 3(c) shows a considerably higher scatter in the results,
413 with a significantly lower accuracy in the prediction of the reliability index due to the fact that Eq. 18
414 does not explicitly consider load factors or the variability of the load effects in the formulation, and
415 that it adopts fixed values of the sensitivity factors α_R and α_E . The values of the sensitivity factors α
416 change significantly depending on the load cases, load ratios and target reliability indices considered
417 in the calculation. In the FORM reliability calibrations carried out in this paper for the Eurocode
418 framework, for example, the sensitivity factors for the resistance α_R ranged between 0.26-0.57, while
419 values ranging between -0.80 and -0.96 were observed for the sensitivity factors of the loads α_E .
420 These values are significantly different, for many of the load ratios considered, from the α -values
421 prescribed in prEN 1990 [27] ($\alpha_R = 0.8$ and $\alpha_E = -0.7$), even if the $0.16 < \sigma_E/\sigma_R < 7.6$ condition
422 stated in Section 2.4 is fulfilled. However, when the results corresponding to the β -values relevant to
423 the Eurocode are analysed (i.e., $\beta = 3.8$), it can be appreciated that the $\beta_{pred}/\beta_{FORM}$ ratios for
424 gravity loads are very close to unity.

425 The analysis of the results also indicates that for the ranges of \bar{R}/R_n and V_R factors investigated in
426 this paper (see Table 2), the accuracy of the estimated reliability indices is uniform for all the load
427 cases and simplification methods, while the influence of the dead-to-live load ratio is found to be
428 more important, with the $\beta_{pred}/\beta_{FORM}$ ratios closest to unity being aligned with the lowest values of
429 G_n/Q_n for the FOSM-based simplified expressions (as demonstrated by the results shown in Figure
430 3(a) and (b)), and with the highest G_n/Q_n ratios for the Eurocode semi-probabilistic approach (see
431 Figure 3(c)). This is in line with the differences observed between the FORM sensitivity factors and
432 the fixed values of α_R and α_E defined in prEN 1990 [27], since the biggest differences in the α -values
433 correspond to the lowest G_n/Q_n ratios, while the sensitivity factors closest to the prEN 1990 values
434 are observed for the highest G_n/Q_n load ratios. The fact that the accuracy of Eq. 18 improves as the
435 β -values get closer to the target reliability index and for high G_n/Q_n ratios suggests that the α -values
436 prescribed in prEN 1990 [27] were calibrated using these values as reference.

437 The statistics of the $\beta_{pred}/\beta_{FORM}$ ratios are reported in Table 3 for the different design approaches
438 and load cases analysed, including the mean values, the coefficients of variation and the minimum-to-
439 maximum ratio ranges. Note that the results presented in Table 3 correspond to frames with different
440 dead-to-live and gravity-to-wind load ratios, and that only results lying in the area of interest
441 $\beta_{FORM} = 2.5 - 3.8$ have been considered. From these results, it can be concluded that the reliability
442 indices can be estimated with average differences of about 5% for the US framework and between 5-
443 10% for the Eurocode framework using the FOSM-based simplified expressions given in Eq. 4 and
444 Eq. 6, with significantly low variations. For the Eurocode semi-probabilistic approach, the accuracy
445 in the predicted β -values is significantly lower, although $\beta_{pred}/\beta_{FORM}$ ratios close to unity are
446 observed in the vicinity of the reliability index relevant to the Eurocode.

447 4.2. ASSESSMENT OF THE ESTIMATED RESISTANCE ϕ AND PARTIAL SAFETY γ_M

448 FACTORS FOR A GIVEN LEVEL OF RELIABILITY

449 Following a similar approach to that adopted for the assessment of the estimated reliability indices
450 using the simplified expressions reported in Section 2, this Section presents the results corresponding
451 to the estimation of resistance ϕ and partial safety γ_M factors using Eq. 5, Eq. 7 and Eq. 17,

452 considering the same load cases and frames investigated in the previous Section. Figure 4 evaluates
453 the accuracy of Eq. 5, Eq. 7 and Eq. 17 by comparing the predicted resistance ϕ_{pred} and partial
454 safety $\gamma_{M,pred}$ factors with the equivalent factors calibrated using FORM techniques, ϕ_{FORM} and
455 $\gamma_{M,FORM}$. Predicted-to-FORM ratios are plotted against the reference β_{FORM} -values, as in Figure 3,
456 and the results are presented separately for the different load cases and simplification procedures
457 investigated. For simplicity, only gravity load results corresponding to dead-to-live ratios of $\zeta = 0.5$
458 and $\zeta = 0.2$ and gravity plus wind load cases are shown. Figure 4 indicates that the accuracy observed
459 for the two FOSM-based simplified expressions (Eq. 5 and Eq. 7) is very similar, since the results in
460 Figure 4(a) and (b) are symmetric about the $\phi_{pred}/\phi_{FORM} = 1.0$ (or $\gamma_{M,pred}/\gamma_{M,FORM} = 1.0$) axis.
461 As for the reliability index, the scatter in the prediction of the partial safety factors γ_M is higher for the
462 Eurocode semi-probabilistic method, but the $\gamma_{M,pred}/\gamma_{M,FORM}$ ratios are close to unity as the β -values
463 approach the reference value of 3.8 for gravity load cases. For gravity plus wind load scenarios, the
464 prediction of the γ_M -factors is less accurate.

465 The results indicate that the FOSM-predicted ϕ -factors for the gravity plus wind load case in the
466 US framework are lower than the corresponding ϕ_{FORM} -values, while the converse is true for gravity
467 loads. This indicates that the prediction of ϕ -factors is conservative for the gravity plus wind load
468 case, and slightly unconservative for gravity loads. It should be emphasized that the results for FOSM
469 and FORM will be same in the particular cases in which R and S are normal, or if R and S are
470 lognormal, for which the FOSM equations are exact. Since for steel structures it is customary to
471 model R as lognormal [13], FOSM and FORM approaches will give similar results if the loads are
472 close to lognormal distributions, although according to the stochastic models traditionally adopted for
473 gravity and wind loads in the literature, the loads to which structures are subjected will typically be a
474 combination of a normal distribution and an Extreme Type I distribution (see Table 1). These can
475 differ significantly from lognormal distributions, especially for small gravity-to-wind load ratios.
476 Likewise, it is found that the γ_M -factors estimated using Eq. 7 are lower than those calibrated using
477 the FORM method for gravity loads in the Eurocode, while the prediction of γ_M -factors is
478 conservative for gravity plus wind loads. On the contrary, in the case of the Eurocode semi-

479 probabilistic approach the prediction of the partial safety factor is in general unconservative for the
480 gravity plus wind load combinations in the range of reliability levels close to 3.8 and conservative for
481 gravity load cases, although with significant errors. In line with the results reported in the previous
482 Section, the accuracy in the estimation of the ϕ and γ_M -factors was found not to be significantly
483 influenced by the \bar{R}/R_n (or \bar{R}/R_k) and V_R values or the type of material.

484 Finally, Table 3 reports the mean values, coefficients of variation and minimum-to-maximum
485 ranges of the ϕ_{pred}/ϕ_{FORM} and $\gamma_{M,pred}/\gamma_{M,FORM}$ ratios calculated considering all the frames and
486 load ratios investigated. According to these values, Eq. 5 and Eq. 7 provide accurate estimations of
487 the resistance ϕ and partial safety γ_M factors for the gravity and gravity plus wind load cases, with
488 average differences between 3-7% and 5-8% for the US and Eurocode frameworks, respectively, and
489 with low coefficients of variation. On the other hand, the estimation of partial safety factors using the
490 semi-probabilistic approach detailed in Annex D of prEN 1990 [27] provides average differences of
491 13% and 5% with the FORM-based values for the gravity and gravity plus wind load cases,
492 respectively, in the area of interest: β_{FORM} ranging from 2.5 to 3.8. While the mean accuracy of this
493 approach is reasonable, the range of $\gamma_{M,pred}/\gamma_{M,FORM}$ ratios obtained is 0.74-1.41, as shown in Table
494 3, too scattered to be used in code calibration, although the accuracy for reliability indices of around
495 3.8 is notably better according to the results shown in Figure 4(c). As highlighted in the previous
496 Section, the values of the sensitivity factors α – and therefore the accuracy of the prEN 1990 semi-
497 probabilistic approach – depend on the load ratios and the target reliability indices considered.
498 Providing a fixed value of these sensitivity factors can be useful, but it is necessary to limit the
499 applicability of this expression when used for the calibration of partial safety factors. According to the
500 reliability results analysed in this paper, and considering that an acceptable estimation of γ_M -factors
501 remains in the $\pm 10\%$ range, it is recommended to limit the applicability of Eq. 17 to $\beta \in [2.5 - 3.5]$
502 for wind load cases with G_n/W_n ratios in the range of 0.10-0.33, and to $\beta \in [2.5 - 4.0]$ for gravity
503 load ratios between $\zeta = 0.2$ and $\zeta = 0.5$, ranges that are in the vicinity of the Eurocode target
504 reliability index.

505 5. DIRECT COMPARISON OF THE US AND EUROCODE FRAMEWORKS

506 The simplified expressions to estimate the required resistance ϕ and partial safety γ_M factors
507 corresponding to specific target reliability indices β_0 (Eq. 5, Eq. 7 and Eq. 17) can be used to derive
508 relationships to directly compare the US and Eurocode frameworks. These relationships allow not
509 only to carry out a comparative assessment of the reliability levels present in the two design
510 frameworks, but can also assist specification committees in developing suitable resistance ϕ factors,
511 corresponding to the particular levels of reliability required by the specification under consideration,
512 using the partial safety factors γ_M prescribed by an independent committee for a different value of
513 target reliability β_0 (or vice versa, to estimate partial safety factors γ_M from existing resistance ϕ
514 factors considering the suitable reliability frameworks and target β_0 values in each case). Expressions
515 for these two scenarios are developed in this Section. Both of the two alternative approaches for the
516 estimation of partial safety factors considered in this paper (equations based on FOSM and semi-
517 probabilistic approaches) are investigated. For each approach, the results are assessed using the
518 resistance and partial safety factors derived from the FORM analyses introduced in Section 3 in order
519 to evaluate how the inaccuracies observed in the previous Section for the estimation of the individual
520 γ_M and ϕ factors compound when Eq. 5, Eq. 7 and Eq. 17 are combined.

521 5.1. DEVELOPMENT OF DIRECT COMPARISON EXPRESSIONS USING FOSM

522 Combining the expressions to estimate resistance ϕ and partial safety γ_M factors obtained from FOSM
523 approaches (Eq. 5 and Eq. 7, respectively), the relationship given by Eq. 19 can be derived, which
524 directly relates the US and Eurocode design frameworks. The equation can be used for different
525 loading cases through the definition of suitable C_{US} , C_{EN} , $V_{S,US}$ and $V_{S,EN}$ coefficients, as indicated in
526 Section 2.3. Nevertheless, Eq. 19 can be further simplified for different load combinations in some
527 particular cases, as presented in this Section, since Eq. 5 and Eq. 7 have been derived using similar
528 procedures and assumptions.

$$\phi \cdot \gamma_M = \frac{C_{US}(\bar{R}/R_n)_{US} \exp\left(\beta_{EN} \sqrt{V_R^2 + V_{S,EN}^2}\right)}{C_{EN}(\bar{R}/R_k)_{EN} \exp\left(\beta_{US} \sqrt{V_R^2 + V_{S,US}^2}\right)} \quad \text{Eq. 19}$$

529 5.1.1. Calibration coefficients, C

530 According to the definition of the calibration coefficients C given in Section 2.3.1 for the gravity load
531 case, the C_{US} and C_{EN} terms depend on the G_n/Q_n ratio, the load combination and the stochastic
532 models that characterize the effects of dead and live loads. Since these inputs are different in the US
533 and Eurocode frameworks, the C_{US} and C_{EN} coefficients will typically be different, as illustrated in
534 Figure 5, where the values of the C_{US} and C_{EN} coefficients are plotted as functions of the dead-to-live
535 load ratio ζ . Nevertheless, Figure 5 also demonstrates that the C_{EN}/C_{US} ratio shows a nearly constant
536 value of 1.16 in the range of common G_n/Q_n ratios, so it is possible to simplify the C_{US}/C_{EN} term in
537 Eq. 19 for the gravity load case by the constant value of $1/1.16 = 0.86$. On the contrary, the C_{US} and
538 C_{EN} ratios are very similar when the gravity plus wind load case is considered, since from the
539 equations presented in Section 2.3.2, the calibration coefficients for wind loads result in $C_{US} = 2.13$
540 and $C_{EN} = 2.14$. Hence, the C_{US}/C_{EN} term in Eq. 19 can be ignored for this load case.

541 5.1.2. Coefficient of variation for the load effect, V_S

542 From the expressions presented in Section 2.3.1 for the calculation of the coefficient of variation for
543 the load effect V_S , it is also evident that V_S depends on the G_n/Q_n load ratio and load statistics, which
544 are different, in principle, for the two design frameworks investigated. Figure 6 shows the values of
545 the V_S coefficients for the US and Eurocode frameworks for varying G_n/Q_n load ratios, which
546 demonstrate that although the $V_{S,US}$ and $V_{S,EN}$ coefficients are different, they can be reasonably
547 considered as equal. The maximum difference between the two coefficients of variation is about 6%
548 (see the $(V_{S,US}-V_{S,EN})/V_{S,EN}$ curve in Figure 6), which occurs for a dead-to-live load ratio of $\zeta = 1.0$.
549 For the gravity plus wind load case, the values of the $V_{S,US}$ and $V_{S,EN}$ parameters are equal, since the
550 two design frameworks adopt maximum wind load models with the same coefficient of variation of
551 0.35 (see Table 1).

552 5.1.3. *Bias and coefficient of variation for the resistance, \bar{R}/R_n , \bar{R}/R_k and V_R*

553 The distribution of the resistance of structures (or members) is generally calculated through an
554 analysis of random samples that account for the most influential uncertainties (i.e., geometric and
555 material properties, imperfections, residual stresses, etc.) following statistical models that are based
556 on measurements on real structures. The random samples of resistance can be the results of either
557 advanced finite element simulations or actual test specimens, from which statistical distributions
558 describing the variability of the resistance can be inferred. Hence, these statistical parameters (mean
559 resistance \bar{R} and coefficient of variation V_R) will typically be the same in the different design
560 frameworks, since they are based on real random structures. On the contrary, the value of nominal
561 resistance R_n will usually differ from one design framework to another, because it is based on a
562 certain structural standard. However, these differences depend on the design approach and material
563 investigated.

564 When system-based direct design approaches are considered, the nominal R_n or characteristic R_k
565 resistances in the different frameworks are determined from advanced finite element simulations
566 based on specifications that generally prescribe the same (or very similar) nominal characteristics,
567 such as initial imperfection patterns and magnitudes, residual stresses and material properties. Thus,
568 the resulting $R_{n,US}$ and $R_{k,EN}$ resistances will be very similar when calculated to the US and Eurocode
569 frameworks. However, for some particular cases, such as stainless steel structures, the corresponding
570 material specifications prescribe considerably different nominal properties for each framework
571 [21,22]; hence in these situations, the nominal and characteristic resistances can be significantly
572 different. On the other hand, if member-based reliability calibrations are performed, the nominal
573 resistances will typically be based on analytical expressions incorporated in the relevant specifications
574 (e.g., buckling curves predicting the strength of columns), which can substantially differ depending on
575 the standard considered and produce significantly different $R_{n,US}$ and $R_{k,EN}$ values. Since this paper is
576 concerned with system-based reliability calibrations based on the direct design approach for steel and
577 stainless steel frames, it can be assumed that the $(\bar{R}/R_n)_{US}$ and $(\bar{R}/R_k)_{EN}$ terms in Eq. 19 can be
578 ignored when structural steel frames are analysed, whereas the $R_{k,EN}/R_{n,US}$ coefficient should be kept

579 for stainless steel frame cases owing to the differences in the prescribed nominal material properties
 580 for these alloys.

581 5.2. DIRECT ESTIMATION OF RESISTANCE ϕ AND PARTIAL SAFETY γ_M FACTORS FOR 582 DIFFERENT LEVELS OF RELIABILITY β

583 Considering the simplifications discussed in the previous Section, Eq. 19 can be re-written for the
 584 particular cases in which the US and Eurocode frameworks are compared for structures subjected to
 585 gravity loads (as per in Eq. 20) and under gravity plus wind loads (as per in Eq. 21). These equations
 586 can be further simplified by adopting $R_{k,EN}/R_{n,US} = 1.0$ when structural steel frames are analysed.

$$\phi \cdot \gamma_M = 0.86 \frac{R_{k,EN}}{R_{n,US}} \exp \left[(\beta_{EN} - \beta_{US}) \sqrt{V_R^2 + V_S^2} \right] \quad (\text{gravity load case}) \quad \text{Eq. 20}$$

$$\phi \cdot \gamma_M = \frac{R_{k,EN}}{R_{n,US}} \exp \left[(\beta_{EN} - \beta_{US}) \sqrt{V_R^2 + V_S^2} \right] \quad (\text{gravity plus wind load case}) \quad \text{Eq. 21}$$

587 Eq. 20 and Eq. 21 can be used to propose suitable resistance factors ϕ that meet the reliability
 588 requirements indicated in the US framework (i.e., the target reliability indices $\beta_{0,US}$ discussed in
 589 Section 2.1) based on the partial safety factors γ_M calibrated for the Eurocode frameworks for a
 590 different target reliability $\beta_{0,EN}$ (or vice versa). For the assessment of these equations, this Section
 591 presents the comparison of the resistance ϕ and partial safety γ_M factors estimated using Eq. 20 and
 592 Eq. 21 with the equivalent values obtained using FORM methods. For example, the predicted
 593 resistance factors ϕ_{pred} considered in this Section have been obtained from Eq. 20 and Eq. 21 using
 594 $\beta_{0,US}$ and the partial safety factors calibrated from FORM analyses $\gamma_{M,FORM}$ for the typical Eurocode
 595 target reliability $\beta_{0,EN}$ and the suitable $R_{k,EN}/R_{n,US}$ relationship, depending on the material
 596 considered. In the analysis, the target reliability indices typically assumed in the two design
 597 frameworks have been adopted (see Section 2.1): for the gravity load case, $\beta_{0,US} = 2.5$ and $\beta_{0,EN} =$
 598 3.8 values have been assumed; for the gravity plus wind load case, $\beta_{0,US} = \beta_{0,EN} = 2.8$ is adopted.

599 Figure 7 presents the assessment of the ϕ_{pred} - and $\gamma_{M,pred}$ -factors estimated using Eq. 20 and Eq.
 600 21 against the values that a proper FORM-based reliability calibration would produce (ϕ_{FORM} and
 601 $\gamma_{M,FORM}$) for different load cases. The results are presented separately for the US and Eurocode
 602 frameworks, and different markers have been used for the gravity or gravity plus wind load cases, and

603 for steel or stainless steel frames. The figures also show the $\pm 5\%$ and $\pm 10\%$ intervals. According to
604 the results presented in Figure 7, the prediction of the resistance and partial safety factors is, in
605 general, reasonably accurate, since most of the results lie within the $\pm 5\%$ range for the gravity and
606 gravity plus wind load cases, although the results for the gravity load case are found to be more
607 accurate and less scattered. It is worth mentioning that some of the datapoints corresponding to
608 stainless steel frames included in Figure 7(a) show resistance factors ϕ higher than unity, which can
609 be explained by the high \bar{R}/R_n ratios resulting from the remarkably low yield stress values prescribed
610 for these alloys in the SEI/ASCE 8 [46] Specification, as discussed in [21,22]. Similar observations
611 have also been reported for timber and masonry structures [29]. The mean values, coefficients of
612 variation and minimum-to-maximum ranges of the ϕ_{pred}/ϕ_{FORM} and $\gamma_{M,pred}/\gamma_{M,FORM}$ ratios are
613 reported in Table 4 for the different cases analysed.

614 5.3. DIRECT COMPARISON OF RESISTANCE ϕ AND PARTIAL SAFETY γ_M FACTORS FOR 615 THE SAME LEVEL OF RELIABILITY β

616 The comparison of the resistance ϕ and partial safety γ_M factors calibrated in the US and Eurocode
617 frameworks is not direct, as shown in the previous Section, because the reliability levels required for
618 the two design framework are different (i.e., different target reliabilities are generally adopted).
619 However, Eq. 20 and Eq. 21 can be further elaborated to provide simple expressions that allow a
620 direct comparison of the resistance ϕ and partial safety γ_M factors when the same level of reliability is
621 assumed for the two frameworks, by adopting $\beta_{EN} = \beta_{US}$. In such cases, the exponential terms in Eq.
622 20 and Eq. 21 are equal to unity and thus ϕ and γ_M -factors are related by the $\phi \cdot \gamma_M =$
623 $0.86 R_{k,EN}/R_{n,US}$ and $\phi \cdot \gamma_M = R_{k,EN}/R_{n,US}$ relationships for the gravity and gravity plus wind load
624 cases, respectively. For the particular situations in which $R_{k,EN}/R_{n,US} = 1.0$ (i.e., the steel frames
625 analysed in this paper), these equations can be reduced to $\phi \cdot \gamma_M = 0.86$ and $\phi \cdot \gamma_M = 1.0$. These
626 relationships provide a simple and direct comparison of the equivalent resistance ϕ and partial safety
627 γ_M factors that would be required for the same level of reliability in the two design frameworks. The
628 equation for gravity loads indicates that, in general, the Eurocode framework is less conservative than
629 the US framework for a given level of reliability, since the required γ_M -factors are about 15% lower

630 than the $1/\phi$ factors for equivalent values of β , while for the gravity plus wind load combination the
 631 two frameworks are similar in terms of conservatism. This is also illustrated in Figure 8, which
 632 compares the γ_M -factors required in the Eurocode framework for the gravity and gravity plus wind
 633 load cases with the $1/\phi$ values, assuming an equivalent level of reliability in all cases.

634 5.4. ANALYSIS USING THE EUROCODE SEMI-PROBABILISTIC APPROACH

635 This last Section presents the derivation and assessment of the expression for the direct estimation of
 636 resistance and partial safety factors using Eq. 5 and the Eurocode semi-probabilistic approach for γ_M ,
 637 Eq. 17. The combination of these two equations results in the relationship given by Eq. 22, in which
 638 the term $R_{k,EN}/R_{n,US}$ can be ignored when structural steel frames are analysed, as discussed in
 639 Section 5.1.3, but should be kept for other materials with different nominal properties prescribed in
 640 the relevant US specification and the Eurocode. Further simplifications are not possible in principle
 641 because Eq. 5 and Eq. 17 are based on different backgrounds.

$$642 \quad \phi \cdot \gamma_M = C_{US} \frac{R_{k,EN}}{R_{n,US}} \exp\left(\alpha_R \beta_{EN} \theta - \beta_{US} \sqrt{V_R^2 + V_{S,US}^2}\right) \quad \text{Eq. 22}$$

643 Nevertheless, all parameters in Eq. 22 are basic statistical input information so the relationship can
 644 still be used for the direct estimation of resistance and partial safety factors, as per in Section 5.2, the
 645 accuracy of which is assessed herein. Figure 9 compares the predicted resistance ϕ_{pred} and partial
 646 safety $\gamma_{M,pred}$ factors using Eq. 22 with the equivalent values obtained from FORM analyses for
 647 different load cases, and also depicts the $\pm 5\%$ and $\pm 10\%$ intervals. The target reliability indices
 648 considered in the analysis were those adopted previously, i.e., $\beta_{0,US} = 2.5$ and $\beta_{0,EN} = 3.8$ for the
 649 gravity load cases and $\beta_{0,US} = \beta_{0,EN} = 2.8$ for the gravity plus wind load cases. Note that these
 650 values are within the applicability ranges of β -values for the use of Eq. 17 proposed in Section 4.2.
 651 The results in Figure 9 indicate that the prediction of the resistance and partial safety factors using Eq.
 652 22 is less accurate than when Eq. 20 and Eq. 21 are used (see Section 5.2 and Figure 7), although the
 653 predictions are still reasonable as they lie within the $\pm 10\%$ range, with no significant differences in
 654 accuracy observed for the load cases and design frameworks investigated. Similar results are shown in
 655 Table 5, in which the means, coefficients of variation and minimum-to-maximum ranges of the
 ϕ_{pred}/ϕ_{FORM} and $\gamma_{M,pred}/\gamma_{M,FORM}$ ratios for the different cases analysed are reported.

656 6. CONCLUSIONS

657 First Order Reliability Methods (FORM), traditionally used by specification committees in the
658 calibration of suitable resistance and safety factors, are advanced and iterative reliability calculation
659 procedures. Sometimes, these techniques require input information (e.g., statistical characterization of
660 the system strength and load effects) that might not be readily available in the literature. Thus,
661 simplified expressions that require no iteration but are sufficiently accurate in estimating reliability
662 indices β , resistance factors ϕ and partial safety factors γ_M can be of great interest for these
663 committees and the research community in general to provide a simple cross-check on the more
664 accurate reliability calculations or to provide direct relationships between the reliability results for
665 different design frameworks. This paper presents a set of simple equations to estimate reliability
666 indices β , resistance factors ϕ and partial safety factors γ_M for the US and Eurocode frameworks
667 based on basic First Order Second Moment (FOSM) reliability considerations and the semi-
668 probabilistic approach prescribed in Annex D of prEN 1990 [27] for design assisted by testing. The
669 equations based on FOSM are similar to those prescribed in the AISI S100 [28] Specification to
670 derive resistance factors when strengths are determined through testing, but have been extended to
671 different load cases and design frameworks. The paper also proposes simple interrelationships
672 between the reliability calibration results for the US and Eurocode frameworks that allow a direct
673 comparison between the two design frameworks. The assessment of the different equations against
674 reliability results derived using the FORM method for an extensive database on steel and stainless
675 frames subjected to the gravity and gravity plus wind load cases collected from the literature showed
676 that the differences in the predicted values of β , ϕ and γ_M lie within the $\pm 5\%$ and $\pm 10\%$ ranges
677 when compared to the reference FORM-based values for the FOSM-based approaches. The results
678 also indicated that, to guarantee a similar level of accuracy for the prEN 1990 [27] semi-probabilistic
679 approach, some limitations are required due to the additional simplifications made by this method
680 (i.e., the adoption of fixed sensitivity factors for the loads and the resistance).

681 **ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS**

682 The project leading to this research has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020
683 Research and Innovation Programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Grant Agreement No.
684 842395.

685 **REFERENCES**

686 [1] White D.W., Jeong W.Y. and Toğay O. Comprehensive stability design of planar steel members
687 and framing systems via inelastic buckling analysis. *International Journal of Steel Structures* 16(4),
688 1029–1042, 2016.

689 [2] Surovek A., Camotim D., Hajjar J., Teh L., White D. and Ziemian R. Direct second-order analysis
690 for the design of steel structures. *Proceedings of the Structures Congress*, St. Louis, United States,
691 2006.

692 [3] Surovek A.E., White D.W., Ziemian R.D., Camotim D., Hajjar J.F. and Teh L.H.
693 Recommendations for the use of direct second-order inelastic analysis to design steel frames.
694 *Structural Stability Research Council - Proceedings of the 2007 Annual Stability Conference*, pp.
695 301–316, New Orleans, United States, 2007.

696 [4] Gonçalves R. and Camotim D. A system-based approach for the design of laterally unbraced
697 multi-span steel columns and beams. *Engineering Structures* 135, 10–20, 2017.

698 [5] Wang Y. and Ziemian R.D. Design by advanced elastic analysis: An investigation of beam-
699 columns. *Engineering Journal* 58(2), 123–137, 2021.

700 [6] Ziemian R.D. and Wang Y. Design by advanced analysis - 2016 AISC specification. *Proceedings*
701 *of the International Colloquium on Stability and Ductility of Steel Structures* SDSS-2019, pp. 55–67,
702 Prague, Czechs Republic, 2019.

703 [7] Chan S.L., Liu Y.P. and Liu S.W. Research, theory and practice of second order direct analysis for
704 design of steel and composite structures. *Proceedings of the International Colloquium on Stability*
705 *and Ductility of Steel Structures*, SDSS-2016, pp. 3–13, Timisoara, Romania, 2016.

706 [8] Ziemian R.D. and Abreu J.C.B. Design by advanced analysis – 3D benchmark problems:
707 Members subjected to major- and minor-axis flexure. *Steel Construction* 11(1), 24–29, 2018.

- 708 [9] Manta D., Gonçalves R. and Camotim D. Combining shell and GBT-based finite elements: Plastic
709 analysis with adaptive mesh refinement. *Thin-Walled Structures* 158, 107205, 2021.
- 710 [10] Du Z.L., Ding Z.X., Liu Y.P. and Chan S.L. Advanced flexibility-based beam-column element
711 allowing for shear deformation and initial imperfection for direct analysis. *Engineering Structures*
712 199, 109586, 2019.
- 713 [11] Fieber A., Gardner L. and Macorini L. Structural steel design using second-order inelastic
714 analysis with strain limits. *Journal of Constructional Steel Research* 168, 105980, 2020.
- 715 [12] Walport F., Kucukler M. and Gardner L. Stability design of stainless steel structures. *Journal of*
716 *Structural Engineering (ASCE)*, 2021. DOI: 10.1061/(ASCE)ST.1943-541X.0003165.
- 717 [13] Rasmussen K.J.R. and Zhang H. Future challenges and developments in the design of steel
718 structures – an Australian perspective. Proceedings of the 8th European Conference on Steel and
719 Composite Structures (EUROSTEEL 2017). Copenhagen, Denmark, 2017.
- 720 [14] Zhang H., Shayan S., Rasmussen K.J.R. and Ellingwood B.R. System-based design of planar
721 steel frames, I: Reliability framework. *Journal of Constructional Steel Research* 123, 135–143, 2016.
- 722 [15] Zhang H., Shayan S., Rasmussen K.J.R. and Ellingwood B.R. System-based design of planar
723 steel frames, II: Reliability results and design recommendations. *Journal of Constructional Steel*
724 *Research* 123, 154–161, 2016.
- 725 [16] Liu W., Rasmussen K.J.R. and Zhang H. Systems reliability for 3D steel frames subject to gravity
726 loads. *Structures* 8, 170–182, 2016.
- 727 [17] Liu W., Zhang H., Rasmussen K.J.R. and Yan S. System-based limit state design criterion for 3D
728 steel frames under wind loads. *Journal of Constructional Steel Research* 157, 440–449, 2019.
- 729 [18] Liu W., Zhang H. and Rasmussen K.J.R. System reliability-based Direct Design Method for
730 space frames with cold-formed steel hollow sections. *Engineering Structures* 166, 79–92, 2018.
- 731 [19] Sena Cardoso F. System reliability-based criteria for designing cold-formed steel structures by
732 advanced analysis. PhD thesis. The University of Sydney, 2016.
- 733 [20] Sena Cardoso F., Zhang H., Rasmussen K.J.R. and Yan S. Reliability calibrations for the design
734 of cold-formed steel portal frames by advanced analysis. *Engineering Structures* 182, 164–171, 2019.

735 [21] Arrayago I. and Rasmussen K.J.R. System-based reliability analysis of stainless steel frames
736 under gravity loads. *Engineering Structures* 231, 111775, 2021.

737 [22] Arrayago I., Rasmussen K.J.R. and Zhang H. System-based reliability analysis of stainless steel
738 frames subjected to gravity and wind loads. *Submitted to Structural Safety*, 2021.

739 [23] AS/NZS 4100 Steel Structures. Standards Australia, Sydney, Australia, 2020.

740 [24] American Institute of Steel Construction (ANSI/AISC). AISC 360. Specification for Structural
741 Steel Buildings. Illinois, USA, 2016.

742 [25] American Institute of Steel Construction (ANSI/AISC). AISC 370. Specification for Structural
743 Stainless Steel Buildings. Illinois, USA, 2021.

744 [26] Working Group 22 for Eurocode 3, CEN/TC 250/SC3/WG22. prEN 1993-1-14. Eurocode 3:
745 Design of steel structures – Part 1-14: Design assisted by finite element analysis. Brussels, Belgium.
746 *Under development*.

747 [27] European Committee for Standardization (CEN). prEN 1990. Eurocode: Basis of Structural
748 Design. Draft Document. Brussels, Belgium, 2020.

749 [28] American Iron and Steel Institute (AISI). AISI S100-16. North American Specification for the
750 Design of Cold-Formed Steel Structural Members. Illinois, USA, 2016.

751 [29] Melchers R.E. and Beck A.T. Structural reliability analysis and prediction. John Wiley & Sons,
752 Third Edition, 2018.

753 [30] Meimand V.Z. and Schafer B.W. Impact of load combinations on structural reliability
754 determined from testing cold-formed steel components. *Structural Safety* 48, 25–32, 2014.

755 [31] Ellingwood B.R., Galambos T.V., MacGregor J.G. and Cornell C.A. Development of a
756 Probability Based Load Criterion for American National Standard A58. National Bureau of Standards.
757 Special Publication No. 577. Washington D.C., 1980.

758 [32] Ravindra M. and Galambos T.V. Load and resistance factor design for steel. *Journal of*
759 *Structural Division (ASCE)* 104, No. ST9, 1978.

760 [33] American Society of Civil Engineers (ASCE). ASCE 7. Minimum design loads and associated
761 criteria for buildings and other structures. Virginia, USA, 2016.

762 [34] Hsiao L.-E., Yu W.-W. and Galambos T.V. AISI LRFD method for cold-formed steel structural
763 members. *Journal of Structural Engineering (ASCE)* 116(2), 500–517, 1990.

764 [35] European Committee for Standardization (CEN). prEN 1991-1-1. Eurocode 1: Actions on
765 structures – Part 1-1: General actions. Densities, self-weight, imposed loads for buildings. Draft
766 Document. Brussels, Belgium, 2019.

767 [36] European Committee for Standardization (CEN). prEN 1991-1-4. Eurocode 1: Actions on
768 structures – Part 1-4: Wind Actions. Final Document. Brussels, Belgium, 2019.

769 [37] McAllister T.P., Wang N. and Ellingwood B.R. Risk-informed mean recurrence intervals for
770 updated wind maps in ASCE 7-16. *Journal of Structural Engineering (ASCE)* 144(5):06018001, 2018.

771 [38] Gulvanessian H. and Holicky M. Eurocodes: using reliability analysis to combine action effects.
772 *Proceedings of the Institution of Civil Engineers, Structures & Buildings* 158(SB4), 243–252, 2005.

773 [39] Galambos T.V., Ellingwood B.R., MacGregor J.G. and Cornell C.A. Probability Based Load
774 Criteria: Assessment of Current Design Practice. *Journal of the Structural Division (ASCE)* 108(5),
775 959–977, 1982.

776 [40] Tankova T., Simoes da Silva L., Marques L., Rebelo C. and Taras A. Towards a standardized
777 procedure for the safety assessment of stability design rules. *Journal of Constructional Steel Research*
778 103, 290–302, 2014.

779 [41] AS/NZS 4600 Cold-formed Structures. Standards Australia, Sydney, Australia, 2018.

780 [42] Steenbergen R.D.J.M. and Vrouwenvelder A.C.W.M. Safety philosophy for existing structures
781 and partial factors for traffic loads on bridges. *HERON* 55(2), 123–140, 2010.

782 [43] Ellingwood B.R. and Tekie P.B. Wind load statistics for probability-based structural design.
783 *Journal of Structural Engineering (ASCE)* 125(4), 453–463, 1999.

784 [44] Ellingwood B.R. LRFD: implementing structural reliability in professional practice. *Engineering*
785 *Structures* 22, 106–15, 2000.

786 [45] Ellingwood B.R. Probability-based codified design: past accomplishments and future challenges.
787 *Structural Safety* 13, 159–176, 1994.

788 [46] American Society of Civil Engineers (ASCE). SEI/ASCE 8. Specification for the Design of
789 Cold-Formed Stainless Steel Structural Members. Virginia, USA, 2021.

TABLES

Table 1. Load statistics adopted in reliability analyses.

Design framework	Load type	Mean	COV	Distr. type	Reference
US framework	Dead load, G	$1.05G_n$	0.10	Normal	[39]
	Live load, Q	$1.00Q_n$	0.25	Extreme Type I	[39]
	Arbitrary-point-in-time live load, Q_{apt}	$0.25Q_n$	0.60	Gamma	[14]
	Wind load, W	$0.47W_n^\dagger$	0.35	Extreme Type I	[37]
Eurocode framework	Dead load, G	$1.00G_k$	0.10	Normal	[38]
	Live load, Q	$0.80Q_k$	0.25	Extreme Type I	[21]
	Arbitrary-point-in-time live load, Q_{apt}	$0.20Q_n$	0.60	Gamma	[21]
	Wind load, W	$0.70W_k^*$	0.35	Extreme Type I	[38]

[†] Wind loads in ASCE 7 [33] are based on a return period of T=700 years.

* Wind loads in EN 1991-1-4 [36] are based on a return period of T=50 years.

Table 2. Summary of assembled database on steel and stainless steel frames for reliability calibrations.

Frame type	Load case	No. of frames	Range of \bar{R}/R_n	Range of V_R	Reference
HR planar sway frames	G+Q	24	1.02-1.11	0.09-0.11	[14,15]
HR planar sway frames	G+Q _{apt} +W	27	1.06-1.36	0.11-0.15	[14,15]
HR planar braced frames	G+Q	57	1.00-1.10	0.07-0.12	[14,15]
HR 3D sway frames	G+Q	40	0.97-1.12	0.09-0.14	[16]
HR 3D sway frames	G+Q _{apt} +W	24	1.07-1.38	0.10-0.16	[17]
HR 3D braced frames	G+Q	22	0.99-1.09	0.09-0.12	[16]
CF HSS 3D sway frames	G+Q	30	0.99-1.08	0.09-0.12	[18]
CF HSS 3D braced frames	G+Q	34	0.97-1.08	0.09-0.11	[18]
CF HSS 3D sway frames	G+Q _{apt} +W	24	1.11-1.39	0.10-0.18	[18]
CF portal frames	G+Q	8	0.99-1.08	0.07-0.10	[19]
CF portal frames	G+W	12	0.93-1.28	0.05-0.18	[20]
CF HSS stainless steel portal frames	G+Q	6	1.18-1.37	0.09-0.12	[21]
CF HSS stainless steel portal frames	G+W	18	1.12-1.32	0.09-0.11	[22]

HR: hot-rolled

CF: cold-formed

HSS: hollow structural section

Table 3. Assessment of the simplified expressions to estimate the reliability index β and the resistance ϕ or partial safety γ_M factors in different design frameworks and load cases (Eq. 4-Eq. 7, Eq. 17, Eq. 18).

Design framework	Load case		$\frac{\beta_{pred}}{\beta_{FORM}}$	$\frac{\phi_{pred}}{\phi_{FORM}}$ or $\frac{\gamma_{M,pred}}{\gamma_{M,FORM}}$
US framework (FOSM)	Gravity loads	Mean	1.05	1.03
		COV	0.034	0.020
		Min-Max	0.91-1.22	0.97-1.12
	Gravity plus wind loads	Mean	0.94	0.93
		COV	0.007	0.006
		Min-Max	0.91-0.97	0.91-0.96
Eurocode framework (FOSM)	Gravity loads	Mean	1.09	0.95
		COV	0.028	0.020
		Min-Max	0.96-1.23	0.87-1.02
	Gravity plus wind loads	Mean	0.94	1.08
		COV	0.009	0.007
		Min-Max	0.90-0.96	1.06-1.12
Eurocode framework (EC-0 [27])	Gravity loads	Mean	0.63	1.13
		COV	0.361	0.056
		Min-Max	0.03-1.76	0.90-1.30
	Gravity plus wind loads	Mean	1.27	0.95
		COV	0.262	0.128
		Min-Max	0.43-2.89	0.74-1.41

Table 4. Assessment of the expressions directly comparing the reliability for different frameworks and load cases based on FOSM (Eq. 20 and Eq. 21).

Design framework	Load case		$\frac{\phi_{pred}}{\phi_{FORM}}$ or $\frac{\gamma_{M,pred}}{\gamma_{M,FORM}}$
US framework	Gravity loads	Mean	0.97
		COV	0.014
		Min-Max	0.94-0.99
	Gravity plus wind loads	Mean	1.03
		COV	0.031
		Min-Max	0.98-1.12
Eurocode framework	Gravity loads	Mean	0.97
		COV	0.014
		Min-Max	0.94-0.99
	Gravity plus wind loads	Mean	1.03
		COV	0.031
		Min-Max	0.98-1.12

Table 5. Assessment of the expressions directly comparing the reliability for different frameworks and load cases based on the Eurocode semi-probabilistic approach (Eq. 22).

Design framework	Load case	$\frac{\phi_{pred}}{\phi_{FORM}}$ or $\frac{Y_{M,pred}}{Y_{M,FORM}}$	
US framework	Gravity loads	Mean	1.05
		COV	0.025
		Min-Max	0.98-1.10
	Gravity plus wind loads	Mean	0.96
		COV	0.045
		Min-Max	0.89-1.10
Eurocode framework	Gravity loads	Mean	1.05
		COV	0.025
		Min-Max	0.98-1.10
	Gravity plus wind loads	Mean	0.96
		COV	0.045
		Min-Max	0.89-1.10

FIGURES

Figure 1. Graphic definition of the reliability index β and the probability of failure P_f .

Figure 2. Comparison between the semi-probabilistic and FOSM approaches for the estimation of partial safety factors γ_M for different load cases.

Figure 3. Assessment of the simplified expressions to calculate reliability indices β for different load cases and design frameworks: a) US-FOSM, b) EN-FOSM and c) EN-semi probabilistic.

Figure 4. Assessment of the simplified expressions to calculate resistance ϕ or partial safety γ_M factors for different load cases and design frameworks: a) US-FOSM, b) EN-FOSM and c) EN-semi probabilistic.

Figure 5. Comparison of the calibration coefficients C for the US and Eurocode frameworks for gravity load cases.

Figure 6. Comparison of the coefficients of variation for the load effect V_S for the US and Eurocode frameworks for gravity load cases.

Figure 7. Assessment of the expressions directly relating the reliability of different design frameworks based on FOSM (Eq. 20 and Eq. 21).

Figure 8. Comparison of the resistance ϕ and partial safety γ_M factors for the US and Eurocode framework for a constant level of reliability.

Figure 9. Assessment of the expressions directly relating the reliability of different design frameworks based on the Eurocode semi-probabilistic approach (Eq. 22).